

Figure1: The inhibition zones of plant extract against multi-drug resistant bacterial (*Shigella flexneri* Isolate 5 and isolate 8)

Figure 2: The inhibition zones of plant extract against multi-drug resistant bacterial (*Salmonella enterica* Isolates and isolate 5).

Figure3. Gel electrophoresis of PCR product of 16s rRNA gene among *Salmonella enterica* isolates,

Figure 4. Gel electrophoresis of PCR product of 16s rRNA gene among *Shigella flexneri* isolates

Figure 5: Bio film and Antibiofilm activity